

Supplementary materials for the paper “Assessing attitudes towards evidence-based software engineering in a government agency”

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ABSTRACT

Supplementary materials to the paper “Assessing attitudes towards evidence-based software engineering in a government agency”. It includes additional information on the design, conduct of the research as well as the characteristics of the data analysis process. March 2022.

This document presents supplementary material to our study “Assessing attitudes towards evidence-based software engineering in a government agency”. In our study, we investigated the potential value of EBSE in the context of the Uruguayan E-Government agency (AGESIC). To achieve this, our work involved three research instances subject to specific methodologies and of which a detailed report is necessary.

- In a preliminary stage, to better understand the challenges in using EBP we conducted a rapid review searching for secondary studies on its adoption.
- In a first stage, we conducted an EBSE awareness lecture to AGESIC members, followed by a focus group session to study their perceptions on the value and limitations of EBSE.
- In a second stage, we followed up our investigation with a survey that sought to establish whether the ideas presented in the EBSE lecture had had any impact on the agency working practices.

Due to the fact that the information required to fully report the conduct of a qualitative study (i.e., [12, 22]) like ours exceeds the size limits of the original paper, details of the design, conduct, and data analysis of our study are presented here. It is worth noting that ethical considerations are explained in detail in the original paper, so we do not repeat them here.

1. Rapid review on EBP adoption

Pizard planned and conducted a rapid review in June 2019, which was then updated in January 2020. The objective was to search for secondary studies on the adoption or impact of EBP or systematic reviews. It was conducted in SCOPUS with the following search string: *TITLE-ABS ((adoption OR transfer) AND "evidence based" AND ("systematic review" OR "mapping study" OR "systematic literature review" OR "scoping study"))*. As a

result, 278 candidate studies were obtained in the initial search, and in the update 26 were added. From these 304, we selected (by reading title and abstract) the only five studies that were systematic reviews on the adoption or impact of EBP or systematic reviews. To aggregate the studies we used descriptive coding [11] and constant comparative method [19].

Rapid review results can be very limited, but we accepted this limitation since our goal was to gain some knowledge about EBP adoption in other disciplines in order to have more information to compare with our study results.

Table 1 presents the resulting systematic reviews on EBP adoption. For each systematic review we included: reference to its report (1st column), discipline to which it corresponds (2nd column), its objective (3rd column), the period it covers (4th column), the search engines used (5th column), and the papers finally selected from the total number of papers found by the search strategy (6th column).

2. Focus Group design and conduct

The focus group was conducted on August 26, 2019 at the agency’s facilities. To design and conduct the focus group, we used the guidelines included in the literature [6, 8, 9]. The details of the research design, conduct and validation are presented below.

Motivation and conditions for collaboration The former director of the Information Technology area division is also a teaching assistant at Universidad de la República. In late 2018, he attended a talk our research group gave on technical debt, which included results from a secondary study. Afterwards, he suggested to us that the concepts of technical debt and evidence-based practice could be useful to the agency. Members of our research group told him that we were doing research on both topics, although he had no detailed knowledge of our research or interest in its results. Subsequently, we began conversations that led to the delivery of two lectures: one on technical debt and the one on EBSE. We also agreed that we would be allowed to study the participants’ views of EBSE.

Participants’ selection. A call for participation via email was made within the Information Technology area of AGESIC. Below we reproduce the lecture invitation briefing

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ORCID(s):

Study	Discipline	Purpose of study	Period	Search engines	Papers
[17]	Social workers	EBP orientation, attitudes and implementation	2003-2012	Academic Search Complete, Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL) Plus, American Psychological association databases (e.g., Psych info and Psych Articles), Medline, Journal Storage (JSTOR), and Science Direct	32/ 2302
[4]	Healthcare policy	Strategies to promote the impact of SLRs	up to 2/2010	Pubmed, CINAHL, The Cochrane Library (including the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, DARE, Methods Studies, Technology Assessments and Economic Evaluations) and ISI Web of Science	11/768
[24]	Occupational therapists	Attitudes, knowledge, and implementation of EBP	2000-2012	Academic Search Complete, Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature Plus, PsycARTICLES, Ingenta, Medline, Science Direct, and Journal Storage	32/12990
[18]	Physiotherapy	EBP adoption - barriers, enablers and interventions	2002-2012	Academic Search Complete, Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature Plus, American Psychological Association databases, Medline, Journal Storage, and Science Direct	32/NS
[15]	Medicine	Barriers to EBP adoption	2000-2013	PubMed, Scopus, Cochrane library, Web of knowledge, Pro Quest, Magiran (Persian database) and SID (scientific information database – Persian database) databases	106/2592

Table 1: Some systematic reviews on EBP adoption on different disciplines

sent to the members of the Information Technology area of AGESIC.

Lecture. Introduction to evidence-based software engineering.

Places. 25 people

Description of the topic.

In general, knowledge is derived from evidence through a process of interpretation. This occurs, for example, when a scientist studies medical records to show that smoking tobacco causes lung cancer. In areas with empirical or experimental research, the evidence is obtained through observations and measurements, the results of which are reported in one or more scientific publications. In the relatively recent past, in order to have the most current knowledge on a subject, it was common for an expert to review the publications that he believed were most relevant and current. These traditional reviews have biases related to the experience of the researcher, their subjectivity, and they are not entirely reproducible.

To improve the aggregation of evidence, evidence-based practice (EBP) emerged for medicine in the 1970s. The EBP seeks to use an objective, rigorous and planned approach to select relevant studies and to synthesize the results of those studies. The methodological rigor makes the results more reliable since it is possible to study the procedure carried out to obtain it as well as to reproduce it. In medicine, EBP has been essential to help control risk factors for heart attack and stroke, to transform HIV from a fatal to a chronic infection, to test drugs for hepatitis C, and to improve treatments for some types of cancer.

The techniques used in EBP are called secondary studies, since they perform the aggregation of evidence from other studies (called primary studies). The main secondary study is the systematic literature review (SLR). SLRs make it possible

to collect and synthesize evidence from different sources in a more objective and rigorous way.

The introduction of EBP in the area of software engineering began in 2004, called EBSE, and was widely accepted by researchers. It is estimated that more than 200 secondary studies have been published during the first ten years.

Meeting objective. To provide a brief introduction to evidence-based software engineering and the main practical aspects of using evidence. During the meeting, the main fundamentals of research in software engineering and a case of application of a SLR in software engineering will be presented. This lecture will help participants understand the report and results of a secondary study, they will see how it is possible to use the evidence obtained through this type of study.

Attendee profile. Practitioners of the software industry. It is not limited to professionals with university degrees in the area, but it is sufficient that they have been linked to at least one software development or implementation project.

Pre-lecture Questionnaire We created a non-compulsory pre-lecture questionnaire in Google forms and sent it to all those Agency staff who had confirmed their attendance. The translation of the questions (originally in Spanish) is shown below.

S1 What is your position or role within the organization? Explain very briefly what activities you do.*

S2 How do you obtain information to support decision making, eg. choose a technology?*

- Talking to colleagues.
- Reading blogs or internet forums.

- Reading books.
- Attending events or workshops.
- Studying what others do (companies or agencies).
- Reading specialized magazines.
- Other...

S3 How old are you?*

S6 What is your highest completed level of education?*

- Elementary School
- High School
- University Degree
- Specialization or Master's Degree
- PhD

S8 What is your reading comprehension level in English?*

- Very bad, Low, Good, Very good, Excellent.

Technical initial briefing. The initial presentation had the following content:

- *Software Engineering Research* - Brief introduction to research, software engineering research, and scientific publications (e.g., purpose, parts and types of a research paper).
- *Evidence-based software engineering* - Brief introduction to EBSE, including: review process, methods within EBSE and types of issues that can be addressed with EBSE.
- *Adoption of EBSE* - Brief introduction to using an SLR. For this, we presented an SLR, published in Spanish (participants' mother tongue) and with a topic of potential interest to the participants [25]. Each stage of the review process was explained indicating its elements in the example. An example of EBSE in action applied to the industry was also briefly presented [5].

Discussion sessions design. Thirteen agency staff attended the lecture but only eleven attendees agreed to take part in the discussion, but one of them participated only in the combined session. In a first stage, the participants worked in **group sessions**. Two groups were formed (without any segmentation strategy), each one with five participants and a moderator. They were asked to discuss the benefits and limitations of EBSE. They were encouraged not only to say whether EBSE would be useful or not, but also to raise arguments or situations that would support their position. In a second stage, in a **combined session**, each group shared and discussed their reflections with the other group. In both sessions took approximately 20 minutes.

Only the 11 participants and the three university researchers staff who ran the focus group were present during the discussion sessions.

Moderator roles Pizard (R1) made the initial presentation and gave the focus group instructions. Pizard's main PhD research concern is the use of evidence-based practice

in SE and this study is part of his work. In particular, he has been studying barriers and facilitators in EBSE adoption. Recently, he authored a study of EBSE and systematic review training intended for university students [13].

Both moderators, Cecilia Apa and Fernando Acerenza (R2 and R3 in transcripts), were active researchers and were teachers of at least one of the three courses on EBSE and SLRs that were taught in recent years at our university. However, they had no vested interest in the success or failure of the present study.

All researchers had eight years or more experience of conducting lectures and tutorials. Both Apa and Pizard hold a Master's degree in Computer Science, while Acerenza has a Master's degree in Software Engineering.

Moderators had been advised to minimize intervening in the discussion so as not to influence the results. However, they could intervene when a participant made a very obvious misinterpretation of EBSE, or it was necessary to clarify something to continue the discussion.

In addition, the moderators were instructed to ensure that all the participants had the opportunity to express their opinion. This is important in order to mitigate three risks: the negative influence of authority relations [8] (i.e., some managers participated in the activity), that more assertive participants dominate the discussions, or that the audio recordings would discourage participation [10].

Discussions in both groups began with an open brainstorming session about EBSE pros and cons and ended with the moderator listing the points that were raised seeking to confirm them and expand the discussion. As requested, the moderators restricted their interventions to clarification, for example, asking a participant to provide a better explanation, or to give an example to support their statements. Also, in one group, the moderator had to explain the concept of mapping study. It was not necessary for the moderators to undertake any special actions to ensure individual participation. All participants were actively involved in the discussion.

Relevant study design decisions. Some important design decisions made relate to: participants' understanding of EBSE and study location.

As EBSE was a novel concept for most of the participants, there was a risk that they misinterpret some of its aspects or the purpose of the focus group. In order to mitigate this, we adopted two strategies, a simple presentation was prepared and specially adapted to the participants, and special attention was paid during the data analysis to identify possible misinterpretations.

The location choice is an issue with certain consequences [1]. We were invited to hold the meeting at the agency's facilities. We did not propose an alternative, since we believe that conducting the study at the agency's location would encourage a high level of participation. Any off-site location would involve moving participants around town and risk needing to conduct the study outside of the participants normal working hours, two issues that would discourage participation.

Participant validation. In December 2020, we contacted the agency and sent participants a summary of the study results¹. Seven participants responded, five from the IT Optimization division, one from Emerging Technologies, and one from Governance Architecture. They agreed with the results summary and did not suggest any changes.

3. Focus Group Data analysis

Each moderator took notes during the discussions and all the sessions were recorded in audio.

In order to analyze the data we used qualitative thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is generally described as 'a method for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data' [3], and is one recommended approach for analyzing focus group data [20].

As theoretical framework, we used an essentialist or realist approach. In this approach, it is assumed that there is a largely unidirectional relationship between meaning and experience and language, from which it is possible to study motivations, experiences and meanings directly from the expressions of the participants [3].

To carry out the analysis we followed a process adapted from thematic analysis [3, 20], whose main characteristics are: familiarization with the data, initial coding, and identification of themes together with quotes that illustrate them.

We started with a **(1) verbatim transcription** of all audio recordings (including each group session and combined session), generating a total of 19 pages of data.

We had three distinct data sets: group session transcripts, combined session transcripts, and moderators' notes. During the combined session the participants reviewed the opinions they had expressed in the group sessions. The moderators' notes also summarized the group sessions. So, we decided to conduct an in-depth analysis of the group session transcripts and then validated them with the information from the rest of the data set.

Subsequently, transcripts were uploaded to Saturate², a freeware software tool that allows coding and categorizing texts. Then, we used descriptive coding and the constant comparative method [19] to **(2) classify all the positive and negative opinions** of the participants in relation to EBSE made during the group session. Our unit of analysis (and coding) were phrases within each participants' interventions (or an entire intervention, if applicable). We consider an intervention as a fragment of conversation in which a single participant speaks and that can be preceded or succeeded by interventions made by other participants.

Later, we **(3) identified discussion themes from the codes used and we selected quotes to illustrate each theme**. At the end of this step we had an idea of what each theme was and the overall story the data tell about the participants' opinions about EBSE.

We **(4) verified the previous analysis results and extended it using the transcript of the combined session and notes by moderators**. In this step, more insightful quotes or additional elements were included. No new themes arose from this step.

To report the results, as the language used by the participants was Spanish, we worked with an experienced translator to create accurate English versions of the selected quotes.

Up to this point, all the analysis was carried out by Pizard. Subsequently, Acerenza carried out independent checking of the analysis process and its results. Acerenza's suggestions and comments on the analysis were discussed with Pizard until they reached agreement on all issues.

To improve reliability (e.g., to avoid misinterpretation of the data), we had a rigorous analysis process planned in advance. We also used three approaches to improve reliability [14]: systematic tracking of all data, triangulation (recording of audios and notes by moderators) and peer debriefing (i.e., the participation of two researchers instead of only one). In addition, to avoid misinterpreting the data, we used participant validation [14]. For this, as mentioned before, we sent a brief report of the results (including all the selected quotations) to the participants for their validation.

4. Survey Design and Conduct

The main purpose of the survey was to collect the participants' opinions about any impact that knowing EBSE had on their work practices. In addition, to better understand the context in which the participants could make use of the evidence generated by the SLRs, we sought to investigate what type of literature the participants usually utilize.

The survey was conducted simultaneously with the validation of the first stage-results. It was designed and conducted following recommendations and guidelines proposed in the literature [7, 23]. The survey design and conduct considerations are described below.

The participants were the unit of analysis for the survey and the group of AGESIC members, that participated in the first stage of our investigation, was the target population. Participation was optional but not anonymous.

Pizard created the questionnaire based on recommendations from Vallespir and Kitchenham. The final version was reviewed by Vallespir and a study participant (our contact at the agency at that time). In essence, the survey instrument was a self-administered questionnaire with eleven questions (some of which were open questions, to allow the participants to explain their answers more completely). The questionnaire was designed in Google Forms, and was available for one month (from December 23, 2020 to January 26, 2021). The translation of the questions (originally in Spanish) and the flow of the survey are shown below.

S1 Have you used any ideas seen in the EBSE lecture in your working practices?*

- Yes

¹This is a method of validating results sometimes referred to as member checking [2].

²<http://www.saturateapp.com/>

- No [Skip to question 3 and after to question 6]

S2 Indicate what you have done

- Conducting a secondary study (systematic review, mapping study, or rapid review).
- Using an existing secondary study (systematic review, mapping study, or rapid review).
- Using search engines for scientific articles.
- Undertaking a critical appraisal of reports that compare different technologies.
- Other activities, indicate which.

S3 Indicate your first and last name. This information will be used to relate your answers to previous results.*

S4 Of the ideas you used, did you find anything particularly difficult?*

S5 Of the ideas you used or their results, did you find anything particularly useful? * [Skip to question 8]

S6 What is the main reason why you did not use anything seen in the EBSE lecture?*

- The ideas do not fit the way of working.
- I have had no chance or need.
- I tried to use the ideas but was unsuccessful.
- The lecture was not enough for me to understand how to apply the ideas of evidence-based practice.
- Other reasons, indicate which.

S7 Do you think that your knowledge about EBSE could be used in the future? For what?*

S8 Did knowing about EBSE MOTIVATE you to improve or change any activity in your working practices?*

- Yes [Skip to question 9]
- No [Skip to question 10]

S9 In which activities, tasks, problems or situations do you perceive that you have changed after learning about EBSE?*

S10 What kind of literature do you use in your practice at the agency? *

S11 Could you indicate titles or links (this is preferable) to two typical examples of the literature you use?*

To minimize the risk of participants misunderstanding what the survey was about or not remembering the EBSE lecture, we included a paragraph summarizing EBSE purposes and a very brief description of the meeting held in the first stage of this research.

To improve the survey capacity to correctly collect the information required to answer the research question, we took two actions. First, the questions were very specific and the most relevant to our research required participants to provide examples or justifications. In addition, in order to relate the participants' responses with their characteristics (e.g., agency division or academic degree) and their participation in the previous stage of this study, we requested that they identified themselves with their first and last names.

To improve survey participation, we used some principles listed by Smith et al. [21]. We applied brevity by including as few and as specific as possible questions, and designing a survey dynamic presentation (i.e., items and response options participants receive are based on their prior choices). We applied the authority and credibility principles, along with social benefit, by stating that their participation would contribute to our research and to gain a better understanding of EBSE adoption. In addition, as it is specifically recommended to improve the response rate in follow-up studies [16], we asked our contact at the agency to send two reminder emails (spaced approximately by two weeks).

5. Survey Data analysis

To analyze responses of S1, S2, S6, and S8 we counted the number of responses in each response category. In S4, S5, S7, S9, and S10 the textual responses were collated and we used descriptive coding and constant comparative method to classify the responses (without pre-existing codes [S5, S10], or use as initial set of codes based on the activities presented in subsection 5 [S7, S9] and the barriers presented in Table 2 and in subsection 5.2 [S4]). The responses from S11 (i.e., examples of publications used by participants) were listed and mapped with the results from S10 (i.e., types of publications used). The result of this mapping was also classified into the grey literature layers. This analysis was performed by Pizard. Later in a meeting, Pizard and Acerenza discussed the analysis process and its results, agreeing on all the decisions made.

For the open questions (those with textual responses) we sought to use the thematic analysis approach. Although in these cases the data sets were quite small, we decided not only to code but also to identify themes from the codes used, understand what each theme was about, review their consistency, and identify quotes that illustrate each of them.

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